

THE ROLE OF QUESTIONING IN THE CLASSROOM

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ABSTRACT

No one can teach, if by teaching we mean the transmission of knowledge, in any mechanical fashion, from one person to another. The most that can be done is that one person who is more knowledgeable than another can, by asking a series of questions, stimulate the other to think, and so cause him to learn for himself."

One of the most well-known philosopher Socrates who lived 5th century BC said that a brilliance person can prompt someone else by asking a dozen of questions in order to motivate the other to think and learn something new, so that questioning process plays a paramount role in teaching process. By asking a right question we can stimulate students and boost their self-esteem and passion, also their abilities such as analyzing, applying, remembering, evaluating and etc. This paper deals with using Bloom's Taxonomy that can encourage higher-order thinking in their children by building up from lower-level cognitive skills and some techniques that teachers can use in the classroom when asking questions to the whole class to ensure that all children are engaged with the question.

Questioning is one approach that teachers can incorporate assessment for learning

into their daily classroom practice. Teachers regularly engage with students in teaching and learning activities and in order to collaborate the lesson teachers use questioning method. Questioning can be used to quiz the knowledge of the past, with questions requiring factual answers by asking who, what, where, and when etc. As Clarke (2005) has highlighted the inclusion of questioning can have rapid and positive changes in the classroom [3]. It is evident that by questioning students, teacher with lightness can check the comprehension of learners and boost the effectiveness of the lesson.

Questioning effectively in the classroom is closely related with an understanding of Bloom's Taxonomy. Most teacher utilize the Bloom's Taxonomy to plan questions for all levels of cognition. Bloom's Taxonomy was created in 1956 and is a classification system used to define the different levels of

human cognition from the simplest to the more complex. Teachers using Bloom's Taxonomy can encourage higher-order thinking in their children by building up from lower-level cognitive skills [2]. Bloom's Taxonomy has six levels of cognitive processing. They are knowledge, comprehension, application, analysis, synthesis, and evaluation. It is divided into two order such as higher and lower order questioning. Lower-order questions derive from the knowledge and the comprehension levels of Bloom's Taxonomy.

Knowledge. In order to check learners' memory teachers can easily choose knowledge-based type of questions to represent a new topic and ideas for them. By asking such kind of questions learners need to describe, define, match. We can ask them: What it is called? , What did it happened? Who? What types of triangle are there?

Understanding. After depicting a concept and knowledge, teachers have to ask questions that are comprehensible , in other words, it means that teaching and learning activities will measure the understanding of a new topic or assignments. On this stage students need to describe, predict, or compare by asking the following questions: why does he..? explain what is happening in the crater..? what are the key features..?

Application. This category of the questions involve the use of information provided to learners. The application questions are aimed to help students utilize their knowledge through the information provided during the teaching and learning activities. It helps to produce new context, interpret and demonstrate how to do and we make an effort to clarify with the

following questions for instance : what do you think what will happen next? why ? which tool would be best for this?

Analysis. On this stage the main feature of the question is that this form of question works to separate ideas. At a higher level, students will ask with analytical questions, and teachers need to be careful so that students can follow the content of the subject, and the student can analyze , explain and infer the information, also we can analyze these abilities by asking these questions for example: what assumptions are being made..? what is the function of..? what patterns can you see in the way of....?

Synthesis. These kind of questions help to learners come up with a new alternatives and ideas that they took from preliminary information. Additionally, the teacher has to be careful to assist the students till they are able to differ and synthesize question, design, create and compose. there are some alternative questions such as: compose a phrase of your own using a syncopated theory?

what conclusion can you draw? what ways could you test that theory?

Evaluation. At the highest level, evaluation based questions will be given to students, in order to check and judge , evaluate, compare/contrast the quality of comprehension, such kind of questions will be given them for example: which was the better strategy for use? should they develop..? which slogan is likely to have the greatest impact for..?

The other levels of Bloom's Taxonomy belong to the higher-order questions [5]. High-level cognitive questions are the

questions that require students to use higher order thinking ability or reasoning skills. By using these skills, students are not only have to remember only information, but also they use their knowledge to solve, to analyze, and to investigate. These kind of higher-order questions can boost students creating, evaluating, analyzing, applying, understanding, and remembering abilities during the lesson.

Creating. Learners can put components together in order to make up a new product or view, in other words, they are able to generate, design, and develop a topic.

Evaluating. On this stage learners can make judgments and justify decisions such as debate, verify, argue and evaluate.

Analyzing. By analyzing students can differentiate between parts, how they are related to each other by comparing, contracting, criticizing.

Applying. One of the most essential parts in high-level questions is the applying, since learners can utilize the given information in a new way, they try to demonstrate, use, and convert the inverted information by applying it in practice.

Understanding. Students can opposite meaning from oral, written and graphic points through interpret, exemplify, classify, and explain the exposed information.

Remembering. By keeping in mind the student can recall relevant knowledge for a long-term in his or her memory by memorizing, repeating and duplicating.

As Bartlett (2015) states that because of fewer higher-order questions being asked

there is a much smaller percentage of assessing of higher-order cognition. To be more specific it is not to say that lower-order questioning is much more important, at the same time it has a particular role. In other words, it provides the building blocks that higher-order cognition can be built upon [2].

On the other hand, Ellis (1993) claims that many teachers do rely on low-level cognitive questions in order to avoid a slow-paced lesson, keep the attention of the students, and maintain control of the classroom. At the same time, Arends (1994) argues that many of the findings concerning the effects of using lower-level cognitive questions versus higher-level-cognitive questions have been inconclusive. While some studies favor asking high-level-cognitive questions, other studies reveal the positive effects of asking low-level cognitive questions [1]. To make it short, I strongly believe that using low-level-cognitive questions would make the lesson more effective and conclusive, since a student needs to have a deep understanding of the topic in order to answer this type of question.

To conclude our research, the interaction between teacher and learners is the most important feature of the classroom. In order to help learners to acquire basic skills or a better understanding to solve problems, or to engage in higher-order thinking such as evaluation, the role of questions are crucial. Without any doubt, students as well as teachers may ask questions since they are essential tools for both teaching and learning process. In this research review on questioning techniques we analyzed higher-

level and lower-level question types, how can they affect to the learners abilities like evaluating, analyzing, understanding and evaluating etc. We may conclude our research that the efficiency of the answer based on the efficiency of the question, to

maximize the productivity of the students, the teacher and visual classroom materials should be careful of what to ask and how to ask, because asking is the best approach of communicating with the pupils and make them involved in the lesson.

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